

A P O L L O

D7.8: Dissemination Report II

WP7 – Exploitation and Communication

*Authors: Nefeli POLITI-STERGIOU (EVF), Dimitri PAPADAKIS (EVF),
Lefteris MAMAIS (EVF)*

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Lead Beneficiary	DRAXIS Environmental SA				
Lead Author	Nefeli Politi-Stergiou (EVF)	Email	nefeli@evenflowconsulting.eu		
	Evenflow SPRL	Phone	+32 494 44 81 07		
Other authors	Dimitri Papadakis (EVF) and Eleftherios Mamais (EVF)				
Contributions from	All partners				
Reviewer(s)	Polimachi Simeonidou (DRAXIS), Dimitra Perperidou (DRAXIS)				
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Executive summary

The main objective of this deliverable is to **provide a comprehensive overview** of the dissemination, communication and marketing tools and activities developed during M06 – M18 of the APOLLO project. The overall objective of the dissemination and communication activities is to promote the results and benefits of the project to a range of relevant target audiences, in order to foster a sustainable customer base for the future commercial service.

The dissemination and communication material and activities that have been produced or undertaken during this period include:

- maintaining APOLLO's website and social media account, which provide platforms for communicating APOLLO and disseminating news and material related to APOLLO to specific audiences (e.g. younger, technologically-aware farmers on Facebook), and for sharing the latest information on the APOLLO services;
- APOLLO's newsletters, providing information, results and events related to the project;
- specific dissemination tools used and distributed at external conferences such as APOLLO brochure and leaflet and audience-focused presentations;
- representation in media and conferences as well as the publication of scientific papers, enhancing APOLLO's visibility and enabling the development of a solid network amongst agricultural and Earth Observation (EO) academic and industrial stakeholders at both European and regional level.

During these months the scope of media presence and networking activities was to inform and raise awareness to potential users regarding APOLLO services as well as engage them to become trial users and get involved in APOLLO's activities. In addition, networking activities aimed among others at the exchange of information and the fostering of closer scientific and technological cooperation between the project partners and other academic, industrial and governmental partners in the field of Agriculture and Earth Observation services/applications, focused primarily on Europe. Strong networks of stakeholders in both fields is a necessary and important step in the harmonisation of activities and efforts to maximise regional stakeholder's awareness of APOLLO's services.

This document provides short descriptions of the dissemination and communication activities reported from APOLLO partners, and carried out directly by the WP7 team. These include participation in conferences, networking events, media, publications etc. The positive impacts of these activities are already being felt, as exemplified by the requests from media representatives either in the pilot regions or in other EU countries for more information about the project (see Section 2.3) and requests from interested parties for potential cooperation.

1 Communication activities and tools

1.1 Website

The APOLLO website (www.apollo-h2020.eu) serves as the online marketing tool of the project. It provides key information about the project and the future commercial services. APOLLO's website provides access to the following key information in a concise and appealing manner:

- Description of project objectives, partners and funding;
- Public deliverable documents, results and latest news;
- Announcements on project activities and involvement opportunities;
- Promotional materials.

1.1.1 Website statistics

The APOLLO website was put online on the 29th of August 2016, and officially launched in September (M05). Data on website traffic since then have been monitored using Google Analytics. The major statistic indicators are the following:

- **Sessions:** Session is defined as a group of interactions taken by one user within a given time frame (30 minutes) on the website. The number of sessions is an indicator of how many times the site has been visited.
- **Users:** Visitors that have had at least one session within the selected date range (includes both new and returning visitors).
- **Page views:** the total number of times a page has been viewed. Repeated views of a single page are counted.
- **Pages/Session:** average number of pages viewed during a session. Repeated views of a single page are counted.
- **Average Session Duration:** Average time spent by visitors browsing the site.
- **Bounce Rate:** the percentage of single-page visits (i.e. visits in which the visitor enters and leaves the site from the same page, without interacting with the rest of the site).
- Percentage of **New Sessions:** estimate of the percentage of first-time visitors.

The values of the above indicators for all users¹ are recorded in the following table, Table 1.

Indicator	Value
Sessions	2762
Users	1620
New users (M06-M12)	720
Page views	7529
Pages/Session	2.73
Average Session Duration	00:03:04

¹ In the first version of this deliverable, a segmentation of users was applied in order to remove the influence of automated web "crawlers" on the data, by counting only sessions longer than 30 seconds. Due to the limitations of Google Analytics when such segmentation is applied (90-day period only), we have been obliged to remove the filter. As such, the results now represent "all users", which may include some non-human actors.

	(h:m:s)
Bounce Rate	50.43%
New Sessions	58.00%

Table 1: Statistical indicators (M06-M18).

Information on the visitors' behaviour and areas for improvement can be extracted from the statistical data provided by Google Analytics.

Impact/Progress: According to the key performance indicators defined in D7.1 “1st Dissemination, communication and marketing plan”, the overall target is to reach 5000 visitors to the APOLLO webpage. The target for M12 was set to be 500 unique visits. APOLLO not only has achieved to reach 500 unique visitors but has attract during M06-M12 (current reporting period) more than 700 new users. This is a result of the participation of all partners in dissemination activities and well-placed communication activities. As result is very promising for the next phase of the APOLLO project as the project aims to enter a commercial phase.

Sessions

Since launching, **the APOLLO website has received 2762 visits (sessions) from 1620 users.** As can be seen in Figure 1, immediately following the publication of the Newsletters, APOLLO increases the number of its visitors. Visits seem to be stabilised, with a few noticeable peaks occurring as a consequence of various other activities like media presence.

Figure 1: Visitor sessions for the APOLLO website (launch-M18).

As evident in Figure 2, 58% of total visitors to the website were new. At this point, the number of returning visitors is assumed to reflect mainly the project partners. It can be assumed that new visitors are mainly stakeholders interested in learning more about the APOLLO project, coming from the growing network of contacts established via activities such as conferences, media appearances and publications.

Figure 2: New and returning visitors (M06-M18).

Geolocation statistics

This project is co-funded by the European Union

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As can be seen in Figure 3, the majority of visits came from three countries: Greece (22.63% of the total sessions), Serbia (19.30% of the total sessions), Belgium (18.14% of the total sessions) reflecting the home countries of project partners. Spanish visitors represented 6.70% of total sessions. A noticeable number of visits came from other European countries; Italy 3.04% and UK 2.79% as well as Netherlands and Austria. In addition, there are noteworthy visits from the USA 4.09%.

Country	Sessions	% Sessions
1. Greece	625	22.63%
2. Serbia	533	19.30%
3. Belgium	501	18.14%
4. Spain	185	6.70%
5. United States	113	4.09%
6. Italy	84	3.04%
7. United Kingdom	77	2.79%
8. Netherlands	61	2.21%
9. Austria	58	2.10%
10. France	49	1.77%

Figure 3: Visits based on country of origin M06-M18).

These statistics will be increased through the duration of the project as the APOLLO intensifies its dissemination and communication activities and builds solid networking channels and enters a marketing phase.

1.2 Newsletter

During M06-M18 two newsletters were published:

- [Newsletter #2](#), February 2017 (M10),
- [Newsletter #3](#), June 2017 (M14).

Impact

Newsletter Issue	No of Subscribers/Recipients <small>*(incl. the APOLLO team, 28 individuals)</small>	Open rate	Click rate	Clicks per unique opens	Total clicks
Newsletter #1	2 *30	*56.7% (17)	*23.3% (7)	41.2	143
Newsletter #2	48 *76	*39.5% (30)	*14.5% (11)	36.7	20
Newsletter #3	52 *80	*41.8% (33)	*16.5% (13)	40	27
Newsletter #4	62 *91	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a

Table 2: Newsletter subscribers (launch-M18).

Audience growth

Figure 4: APOLLO's Newsletter audience growth through time (launch-M18).

As shown in Figure 4, APOLLO has quadrupled its subscribers over the past year. Top subscriber locations are also shown in the Figure below.

Top locations

Belgium	33.7%
Spain	12.4%
Other	6.7%
Spain	3.4%
Greece	3.4%

Figure 5: Overall top locations from launch until M18. Visits based on country of origin.

Open rates are demonstrated in Figure 6. The first Newsletter shows the best performance so far. This was expected since the first Newsletter subscribers were mainly all consortium members. Therefore, excluding the first Newsletter, it is evident that Newsletter performance increases with time as well as the number of subscribers, as shown above. Based on these statistics we can conclude that this last 12 months APOLLO has succeeded in maintaining a solid audience and reach new individuals as well, across the pilot countries and in the EU in general. These findings are promising for APOLLO's next dissemination phase, which will be more marketing focused.

Campaign performance

Figure 6: Preview of APOLLO's campaign performance over time (lauch-M18).

Impact/Progress: According to the key performance indicators defined in D7.1 “1st Dissemination, communication and marketing plan”, the overall target is to attract 3000 subscribers. Currently APOLLO Newsletter has 62 new subscribers and 50 more during M06-M12 (current reporting period). Although subscriber rate is increasing through time it seems that the Newsletter might not be the major tool to promote APOLLO services to new audience. However, it is a great tool to promote APOLLO to its existing community and retain their interest while engage them as we enter the commercial phase to get more involved in APOLLO and retain them as a pool of early adopters and potential customers.

1.3 APOLLO on Social Media

Both Facebook and Twitter were designed to augment and complement the website as the central channel of stakeholders and potential customer engagement. In addition, a LinkedIn group has been created in order to stimulate debate and discussion around the APOLLO services.

1.3.1 Twitter

APOLLO has established a Twitter presence under the username [@APOLLO_Agri](https://twitter.com/APOLLO_Agri) for amplifying the propagation of news, announcements and publications.

Figure 7: Screenshot from APOLLO's Twitter profile page.

At the end of M06, the APOLLO Twitter account was following 101 other accounts related to the Agricultural sector (i.e. projects, private companies, agricultural professionals, EU agricultural institutions and decision makers) and was being followed by 23 other accounts. Currently (M18) @APOLLO_Agri is following 213 accounts in total, related to the Agricultural and Remote sensing sectors, i.e. 112 more in twelve months, and is being followed by 130 accounts mainly related with Agriculture, Remote sensing (including mainly decision makers, large organisations, academia, projects, scientists) and media. It is evident that APOLLO has increased its target audience by a factor of five over the course of a year.

Impact/Progress: According to the key performance indicators defined in D7.1 “1st Dissemination, communication and marketing plan”, the overall target is to attract 50 followers. Currently APOLLO Twitter has achieved to double the targeted value, yet in its first year. During M06-M12 100 more accounts have followed APOLLO reflecting the results of the dissemination and communication efforts from all partners. A solid network around APOLLO is being established and Twitter seems to be a very good tool to promote the project's activities, news and attract more interest. Supported by and supporting all partner activities, twitter campaign will be considered to be launch after the validation and commercialisation of the APOLLO platform.

1.3.2 Facebook

APOLLO has established a Facebook page for the purpose of reaching out to groups and networks (such as Agri.EU - The Social Network of European Farmers) and for engaging in public conversations with a younger generation of technologically-aware farmers. The APOLLO Facebook page is currently being followed by 102 accounts and has been liked by 104 accounts. Both account groups are mostly individuals related to agriculture such as farmers, crop consultants, non-professional farmers, university students studying agri-related topics, etc. A strong Facebook campaign will follow in the upcoming months as a marketing tool to promote APOLLO platform and services.

Impact/Progress: According to the key performance indicators defined in D7.1 “1st Dissemination, communication and marketing plan”, the overall target is to achieve 300 page “likes”. As indicated above, currently (M12) APOLLO has received 104 “likes”. People seem interested in what APOLLO has to offer and during the period of the life of the project this performance indicator is planned to be achieved and surpassed. Facebook, like the other social channels will complement

other marketing activities and is planned to be mainly used to engage existing network and be used as a tool to spread the news for APOLLO's commercial service.

1.4 Press Kit

A press kit was developed aimed for circulation to journalists. APOLLO's Press Kit is a dedicated sheet for media containing a brief description of the project and its objectives as well as all dissemination material for media and APOLLO's contact point for interviews. The Press Kit is available on the APOLLO website via this [link](#).

Figure 8: APOLLO Press Kit.

1.5 Dissemination activities

Representatives from all APOLLO project partners have promoted the project using the means and channels at their disposal.

1.6 Dissemination material

Dissemination tools finalized and developed during the period M06-M12 comprise the APOLLO brochure and leaflet. The material was designed and developed in line with the APOLLO visual identity and is available both in printable and digital (web-ready) formats. Both the brochure and the leaflet were developed in three different languages, Serbian, Spanish and Greek. So far, approximately 200 copies of brochure, have been disseminated at two major agricultural events InfoAg and ECPA.

1.6.1 Brochure

The APOLLO brochure was designed with the aim of providing a detailed overview of the benefits and advantages of the APOLLO services, with a view to creating brand awareness and attracting new customers. The brochure is also available online on the APOLLO website ([here](#)), whilst the translated versions can be found in the relevant APOLLO mirror sites ([GR](#), [ES](#), [SR](#)).

Figure 9: APOLLO's Brochure (April 2017).

1.6.2 Leaflet

The APOLLO leaflet was designed with the aim of attracting the attention of target audiences with a small number of key messages, triggering brand awareness and encouraging visitors to the website and other social media. The leaflet is also available online on APOLLO's website, ([here](#)) – the translated versions can be found in the relevant APOLLO mirror sites ([GR](#), [ES](#), [SR](#)).

GET INVOLVED

SUBSCRIBE TO OUR NEWSLETTER
Stay informed of our latest news
<http://apollo-h2020.eu/contact/#newsletter>

SIGN UP TO BECOME A TRIAL USER
Be the first to try out the new services!

JOIN US
<http://apollo-h2020.eu/contact>
info@apollo-h2020.com
@APOLLO_Agr
APOLLO H2020 project

PILOTS

The APOLLO services will be co-created, validated and evaluated during two agricultural seasons (May to September, 2017 and 2018), with pilot farmers in three different countries: Greece, Serbia and Spain. APOLLO services cover a wide variety of crop types.

PELLA, GREECE
The Agricultural Cooperative of Pella (AOP), with the help of the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA) and local agricultural consultants, will test the APOLLO services on irrigated cotton and non-irrigated durum wheat crops. Through AOP members, 6300ha of wheat land is dedicated to durum wheat production, and 13500ha to irrigated cotton.

RUMA, SERBIA
The Association of Farmers of the Municipality of Ruma, along with local agricultural consultants, will test the APOLLO services on maize, wheat, soy, vegetables, and fodder crops. Additionally, the consultants involved in the pilot will incorporate the information provided on the test parcels into their advisory practice.

LA MANCHA ORIENTAL, SPAIN
Farmers with large farm holdings along with associations of small farm groupings, such as SOMER, engaged by the La Mancha Or, will test the APOLLO services on a variety of crops over a total area of 100,000ha. APOLLO will act as a facilitator between APOLLO and Spanish farmers.

APOLLO will launch initial services in April 2017

APOLLO
Bringing the benefits of precision agriculture to smallholder farmers
<http://apollo-h2020.eu/>

SERVICES

APOLLO's four services support better decision-making and optimized use of agricultural inputs, reducing waste and increasing yields.

- TILLAGE SCHEDULING**
When and where it is best to till? The APOLLO Tillage Scheduling service will provide daily information on when and where soil tillage should be performed. Tillage is the preparation of the soil before sowing, hence effective tillage is crucial for the beginning of the agricultural season. Environmental and agricultural sustainability and crop quality can be maximised if the soil is tilled at the right time.
- IRRIGATION SCHEDULING**
When and where is irrigation needed? The APOLLO Irrigation Scheduling will provide information on when and where irrigation should be performed for avoiding problems caused to crops by the over- or under-application of water. The farmer can take daily advice on when and in which area it is best to irrigate a crop. Agricultural irrigation uses more fresh water globally than any other activity. Therefore, improving the efficiency of water usage is crucial for environmental and agricultural sustainability.
- CROP GROWTH MONITORING**
What is the current condition of my crops? The APOLLO Crop Growth Monitoring service will enable farmers to keep an eye on their crops' status, from emergence through to harvest, and provide early alerts in case of infestations and nutrient deficiencies. Indirectly, crop growth monitoring can help in delineating different management zones at sub-parcel level for the variable rate application of fertilizers and plant protection products.
- CROP YIELD ESTIMATION**
Forecast crop yield before harvest The APOLLO Crop Yield Estimation service forecasts crop yield before harvest, allowing an assessment of the farmer's expected income, as well as enabling the adaptability of crops and/or varieties to be evaluated, in combination with Crop Growth Monitoring service.

APOLLO AFFORDABLE
Free European Union satellite data from Copernicus and automated processing make APOLLO services affordable for all farmers. The APOLLO services are designed to provide tailored services in state-of-the-art resolution at a low price for all farmers.

APOLLO ACCESSIBLE
Monitor your crops and get reports and alerts anywhere, at any time. The APOLLO services will be available anywhere, at any time, through the web interface and mobile application. The web application will provide full access to all APOLLO services and data, while the mobile application will be used for basic reporting and sending (even offline).

APOLLO EASY TO USE
Developed with farmers for farmers. The APOLLO's four flagship services are being developed based on a farmer-developer co-creation approach. APOLLO services place ease-of-use at the forefront, and are designed to minimise the burden on the end-user.

For more information please contact us: info@apollo-h2020.com

Figure 10: APOLLO's Leaflet (April 2017).

Impact/Progress: According to the key performance indicators defined in D7.1 “1st Dissemination, communication and marketing plan”, the overall target is to distribute 2500 copies of the printed communication material. Taking into account that the dissemination material was ready during M06-M12 (current reporting period) the results should be considered as very optimistic. Mainly because, the 200 copies were distributed in major agricultural events where APOLLO was represented by consortium partners (see Table 3). Updated versions of the dissemination material are planned for the time before APOLLO enters its commercial phase. This targeted indicator is expected to be increased during the next months of the project.

1.7 Conferences

A strategic campaign of event and conference attendance was planned for the lifetime of the APOLLO project and is registered in “D7.1 Dissemination Communication and Marketing Plan”. The aim is to maximise the effect of direct interaction with relevant stakeholders, present the APOLLO solution as part of the programme of speakers and to distribute APOLLO marketing material to attendees. Dedicated presentations were produced by the participating partners to facilitate the promotion of APOLLO in the context of each event. A dedicated [Dissemination Report form²](#) is used to collect reports from partners on the activities in which they have been involved (See Annex I).

1.7.1 Third party conferences, events and workshops

Table 3 summarises the events at which APOLLO was represented, totalling eight conferences and workshops.

Event	Description	APOLLO's involvement
<p>“EU RESEARCH AND INNOVATION IN SUPPORT OF THE EARTH OBSERVATION MARKET”, Brussels, 21-22 September 2016</p> <p>Participation: DRAXIS</p> <p>Session: Breakout Session 1</p> <p>Materials: PPT presentation</p> <p>No. of attendees: 110</p>	<p>The overall objective of this workshop was to explore Research and Innovation (R&I) actions needed for the development of a dynamic Earth observation (EO) market in Europe in relation to the Copernicus and GEO initiatives (Group on Earth Observations). More about the event and APOLLO's ppt can be found here.</p>	<p>The APOLLO project was presented in order to initiate contacts and to build a network across Europe with the members of the EO community. The session was attended by EO data providers, geospatial industrial sector and ICT sector representatives.</p> <p>Presentation title: “An advisory platform for small farms based on EO, APOLLO”, Stelios Kotsopoulos (DRAXIS).</p>
<p>InfoAg2017 St.Louis, Missouri (US), 25-27 July 2017</p> <p>Participation: AGRISAT</p> <p>Session: n/a</p> <p>Materials: APOLLO brochure</p> <p>No. of attendees: ~1600</p>	<p>InfoAg is the premier conference on the practical application of precision agriculture. It features an educational program that includes plenary, breakout, and workshop sessions along with an extensive exhibit hall of leading</p>	<p>Most InfoAg attendees are crop consultants or involved in agricultural retail and farmers. Agribusiness people, university researchers, scientists and government workers. AgriSat representatives had the chance to network with crop consultants and agribusiness people.</p>

² A preview of the Google form can be found in Annex I.

	<p>hardware, software and services vendors to precision agriculture.</p> <p>More about the event can be found here.</p>	
<p>Smart AKIS Regional Innovation Workshop</p> <p>Novi Sad, Serbia, 14 March 2017</p> <p>Participation: UBFCE</p> <p>Session: Group 2: Remote Sensing</p> <p>Materials: PPT presentation</p> <p>No. of attendees: 50, representatives of companies that develop smart solutions in agriculture and farmers, representatives of government</p>	<p>Smart AKIS Regional Innovation Workshop aimed at demonstrating the smart farming technologies currently and potentially available in the regional market. companies that develop smart solutions in agriculture, farmers, representatives of government</p> <p>More information from the event can be found here and the program of the workshop is available here.</p>	<p>In the framework of establishing a solid network within the Serbian agricultural community, Dr. Dragutin Protic and Dr. Milan Kilibarda presented the services and solutions Many stakeholders in agriculture in Serbia were informed about the activities on APOLLO project.</p>
<p>1ST Regional Innovation Workshop: Application of new technologies in agriculture (Smart AKIS)</p> <p>Giannitsa, Greece, 29 May 2017</p> <p>Participation: DRAXIS, AC Pella</p> <p>Session: Presentation of selected new technologies</p> <p>Materials: PPT presentation</p>	<p>This first wave has allowed partners to contrast the findings on farmers' interest and needs on relation to Smart Farming, to showcase some Smart Farming technologies tailored to the farmers' need, and most of all, to start building trust among farmers, researchers, the industry and advisors for the identification of specific innovation projects that will</p>	<p>APOLLO coordinator Dr. Machi Simeonidou (Draxis) attended this event in order to showcase APOLLO and collect observations relevant to the project and make connections with the stakeholders present.</p> <p>Presentation title: "An advisory platform for small farms based on EO, APOLLO", Machi Simeonidou, DRAXIS.</p>

<p>No. of attendees: >49</p>	<p>come up in the second wave of Workshops. The first wave of Innovation Workshops will be followed by 2 more rounds.</p> <p>More information from the event can be found here.</p>	
<p>4th Satellite Soil Moisture Validation and Application Workshop and the CCI Soil Moisture User Workshop</p> <p>Vienna, 18 September 2017 CCI Soil Moisture User Workshop</p> <p>19-20 September 2017 Satellite Soil Moisture Validation and Application Workshop</p> <p>Participation: TUW</p> <p>Session: n/a</p> <p>Materials: n/a</p> <p>No. of attendees: 110 from 21 nations</p>	<p>The Satellite Soil Moisture and Application Workshop brings together experts from all around the world to discuss and reconcile recent methodological advances in the development, validation and application of global satellite soil moisture data.</p> <p>The CCI Soil Moisture User Workshop is similar in scope, but focuses on users of the CCI Soil Moisture products. Users from any relevant application area are invited to present their experiences with the data and provide ideas for future product improvements.</p> <p>More information as well as images from the event can be found here.</p>	<p>insightful discussions were conducted related to these matters, gaining useful insights for the project's scientific advancements.</p>

<p>BioFest 2017: International festival of organic products</p> <p>11-13 October 2017, Subotica, Serbia</p> <p>Participation: UPOR, UBFCE</p> <p>Session: n/a</p> <p>Materials: Article in BioFest's brochure</p> <p>No. of attendees: n/a</p>	<p>The aim of the event is to promote organic production. This year's theme is "IT - an organic vision of the future".</p> <p>More information and the event's program can be found here.</p>	<p>Ugljesa Trkulja (UPOR) attended the event in order to promote APOLLO. In addition, an article focusing on APOLLO project was included in BioFest's brochure (see Figure 11). More than 500 copies of the brochure were available for all attendees.</p>
<p>11th European Conference on Precision Agriculture (ECPA 2017)</p> <p>16-20 July, Edinburgh, UK</p> <p>Participation: Bronze sponsor AgriSat</p> <p>Session: Exhibition booth</p> <p>Materials: ECPA exhibition booth with poster & flyers APOLLO</p> <p>No. of attendees: n/a</p>	<p>In addition to a strong academic programme, the conference feature strong links to industry with practical input through commercial participants and the UK's new Centres of Excellence in Innovation.</p> <p>More information about the event can be found here.</p>	<p>AgriSat was a bronze sponsor of this event and was also present at an exhibition booth. Networking with commercial participants.</p>
<p>11th European Conference on Precision Agriculture (ECPA 2017)</p> <p>16-20 July, Edinburgh, UK</p> <p>Participation: AUA</p> <p>Session: n/a</p> <p>Materials: PPT presentation based on scientific paper</p> <p>No. of attendees: n/a</p>	<p>A well-attended and highly appreciated conference in Precision Agriculture sector. The theme for 2017 was 'Innovating through Research' aimed to enable all involved in Precision Agriculture to participate. Oral and poster presentations on any precision agriculture topic were included.</p>	<p>Evangelos Anastasiou and Spyros Fountas (AUA) attended this event in order to present the scientific publication entitled "User requirements for a satellite-based advisory platform" which was published under the work done in the context of the APOLLO project. APOLLO representatives were also involved in the networking activities promoting APOLLO's science and concept.</p>

More information about the event can be found [here](#).

Table 3: Conferences and workshops at which APOLLO was represented (M6-M18).

Figure 11: APOLLO in BioFest 2017 brochure (October 2017).

Impact/Progress: According to the key performance indicators defined in D7.1 “1st Dissemination, communication and marketing plan”, the overall target is to attend 15 events. APOLLO representatives had already attended 12 events in the first six months of the project’s lifetime. As mentioned above, during M06-M12 APOLLO representatives have attended 8 more events at international, national and regional level. Being a market driven project, APOLLO partners will continue promoting successfully APOLLO services and its science in more events during the next months.

1.8 Publications

Publishing articles in qualified publications guarantees the effective dissemination of specific project results, targeting groups of experts in the sectors addressed by APOLLO. For this reason, a set of conferences and scientific journals were identified. In the scientific domain publishing results in peer-reviewed journals, and in peer-reviewed conferences is the dominant mechanism for knowledge transfer. During the reported period, two scientific conference papers were accepted in peer-reviewed conferences.

- Anastasiou, E., Tsiropoulos, Z., Fountas, S., Osann, A., Protic, D., Simeonidou, M., & Xenidis, L. (2017). “User requirements for a satellite-based advisory platform”. *Advances in Animal Biosciences*, 8(2), 368-371. doi:10.1017/S2040470017000942», ECPA, July 2017.
- Kilibarda M., Protic D., Sekulic A. and Antonijevic O. (2017). “Global daily meteorological data for agricultural services”. Conference on Big Data from Space (BiDS’17), Research, Technology and Innovation, (planned to be held in 28-30 November 2017).

The publication “User requirements for a satellite-based advisory platform” was presented by its lead author PhD candidate Mr. Evangelos Anastasiou at the ECPA conference in Edinburg in July 2017 (as reported in Table 3).

SESSION 1

MONDAY 17 JULY 2017 PENTLAND EAST

SATELLITE APPLICATION

11:30-12:54

Chair - Christelle Gee

11:30	2.368	User requirements for a satellite-based advisory platform <u>E Anastasiou</u> , Z Tsiropoulos, S Fountas, A Osann, D Protic, M Simeonidou, L Xenidis
11:42	3.372	Potential of freely available remote sensing visible images to support growers in delineating within field zones <u>T Crestey</u> , L Pichon, B Tisseyre
11:54	4.377	Using Sentinel-2 images to implement Precision Agriculture techniques in large arable fields. First results of a case study. <u>A Escolà</u> , N Badia, J Arnó, J A Martínez-Casasnovas
12:06	5.383	How remote sensing is offering complementing and diverging opportunities for precision agriculture users and researcher. <u>R Jackson</u> , R C Gaynor, A Bentley, J Hickey, I Mackay, E S Ober,
12:18	6.388	Identification of high-variation fields based on open satellite imagery <u>J H Jeppesen</u> , R H Jacobsen, R N Jørgensen, A Halberg, T S Toftegaard
12:30	7.394	Monitoring crop growth and key agronomic parameters through multitemporal observations and time series analysis from remote sensing big data <u>K Karantzalos</u> , A Karmas, A Tzotsos
12:42	8.400	Water and nutrient management: the Austria case study of the FATIMA H2020 project <u>F Vuolo</u> , L Essl, L Zappa, T Sandén, H Spiegel

Figure 12: Extract from ECPA 2017 detailed program showing the participation of APOLLO's representative to support the scientific publication "User requirements for a satellite-based advisory platform", July 2017.

The number of publications and conference papers is expected to increase as the project's technical team will have more data from technological advances and data from the pilots.

1.9 Media

Since the start of the project on the 1st of May 2016, representatives of the consortium have promoted the project in the media, through regional TV interviews and articles in national news. During the period M06 to M18, APOLLO representatives have promoted APOLLO in several occasions through traditional media including TV, radio and press. The following subsections describe the activities held per country.

1.9.1 Serbia

- [TV coverage and interview](#) in Agro Panorama program (episode 133) on Agro TV channel, published on the 24th April 2017. Dr Dragutin Protic (UBFCE) presented APOLLO services.
- [Interview](#) for Domacin program at TV Prva (national coverage), 18 March 2017, Belgrade. Dr Dragutin Protic (UBFCE) presented APOLLO services.
- Interview in the agricultural show “Farmland of Srem” on Fruska Gora Radio (regional Vojvodina coverage), 10 August 2017, Mr Ugljesa Trkulja (UPOR) presented APOLLO and how farmers actively contribute to APOLLO’s services development.
- [Interview](#) for the agricultural show “Farmland of Srem” on Fruska Gora TV (regional Vojvodina coverage), 09 August 2017, Mr Ugljesa Trkulja (UPOR) presented APOLLO.
- Interview on radio station [Klik917](#) (regional Vojvodina coverage), 15 October 2017, Dr Drautin Protic (UBFCE) presented APOLLO and how farmers actively contribute to APOLLO’s services development.

1.9.2 Greece

- Article and interview on ΥΠΑΙΘΡΟΣ, a Greek journal focused on agriculture, published the 23rd June 2017. Dr Machi Simeonidou (DRAXIS, coordinator) presented how APOLLO is developing services based on farmer needs, how farmers are involved and APOLLO’s pilot phase.

(EN Title: “APOLLO: A platform developed based on farmer needs”)

ΕΠΙΜΕΛΕΙΑ
Βικτωρία Αποστολοπούλου

Υπαιθρος
ΚΩΡΑ

Εισροές & τεχνολογία

ΠΡΑΓΜΑΓΙΑΣΤΙΚΟ ΥΛΙΚΟ
Απαραίτητη η εφαρμογή στρατηγικής που θα επηρξεί στη βιοποικιλότητα της Ελλάδας... 10

APOLLO

Μια πλατφόρμα «φτιαγμένη» από τις ανάγκες των αγροτών

της Βικτωρίας Αποστολοπούλου

Μια πραγματικά εφαρμόσιμη τεχνολογία είναι εκείνη που έχει φτιαχτεί με την πρακτική συμβολή και συμμετοχή των αγροτών. Εκείνη που κατασκευάζεται με βάση τις ανάγκες τους. Η

ΜΕΣΩ ΤΩΝ ΔΟΥΡΥΦΟΡΩΝ,

θα δίνονται ακριβείς οδηγίες για την ποσότητα του νερού, ανάλογα με τις διαφορετικές απαιτήσεις του χωραφιού

πλατφόρμα APOLLO είναι μία από αυτές, αποδεικνύοντας πως η ελληνική γεωργία μπορεί να επιτύχει τη μείωση του κόστους παραγωγής, με τα κατάλληλα τεχνολογικά μέσα.

Η εφαρμογή «APOLLO» αναμένεται να είναι χρήσιμη προσυμμετοχόμενες αγρονομικές συμβουλές στον παραγωγό και είναι σε θέση να κάνει την εκτίμηση του μεγέθους της συ-

γκομίδης. Στην πλατφόρμα, που αναπτύσσεται στο πλαίσιο του Κοινοτικού προγράμματος HORIZON 2020, συμμετέχουν εννέα εταιρείες από πέντε χώρες της Ευρώπης (Ελλάδα, Ισπανία, Αυστρία, Βέλγιο και Σερβία), ενώ συνδυάζει η τεχνολογία από τους τομείς της γεωγραφίας, των γεωργικών υπηρεσιών, των επιστημονικών κέντρων, της τηλεπικοινωνίας μέσω αισθητήρων και της δορυφορικής γεωκόσμησης.

Η εταιρεία Draxis έχει αναλάβει τον συντονισμό, ενώ η καινοπραξία περιλαμβάνει δύο γεωγραφικές ενότητες, τον Αγροτικό Συνεταιρισμό Πέλλας από την Ελλάδα και την Αγροτική Ένωση του Δήμου Ruma στη Σερβία, που θα εφαρμόσουν πιλοτικά και θα δοκιμάσουν τις πρώιμες εκδόσεις των υπηρεσιών.

Η Μάχη Συμεωνίδου, γενική διευθύντρια της Draxis, αναφέρει στην «ΥΧ» πως η βασική αρχή για το «APOLLO» και ο λόγος για τον οποίο ξεκίνησαν να δουλεύουν μια τέτοια εφαρμογή, ήταν η διαπίστωση ότι οι μικροί σε εκτάσεις γεωργοί, αλλά και οι λιγότερο οικονομικά δυνατοί αγρότες, δεν έχουν πρόσβαση στις τεχνολογίες. Ήταν, λοιπόν, πολύ σημαντικό να αξιοποιηθούν οι νέες τεχνολογίες

με τέτοιο τρόπο ώστε να είναι προσβάσιμες και φιλικές στους ανθρώπους που δεν έχουν υψηλή τεχνολογία.

Η συμμετοχή των αγροτών

Το πρώτο βήμα για τη δημιουργία της πλατφόρμας ήταν οι συνεντεύξεις με γεωργούς. «Για έξι μήνες κάναμε συνεκτικές συνεντεύξεις με γεωργούς στο χωράφι τους στην Ελλάδα, τη Σερβία και την Ισπανία. Μίλησαμε μαζί τους και προσπαθήσαμε να βρούμε τι είναι αυτό που θα μπορούσαμε να καλύψουμε. Διαπιστώσαμε, λοιπόν, ότι υπήρχαν κάποια κενά στις καλλιεργητικές φροντίδες, όπου με τη χρήση νέων τεχνολογιών, δορυφορικών και μοντέρνων αγρονομικών, θα μπορούσαμε να δώσουμε κάποιες λύσεις. Οπότε, έγινε εκτεταμένη καταγραφή των αναγκών τους σε σχέση με πιθανή χρήση τέτοιων εργαλείων. Η διαδικασία αυτή, μαζί με τους παραγωγούς, πραγματοποιήθηκε για όλο το δεύτερο εξάμηνο του 2016», αναφέρει.

Με βάση την καταγραφή αυτή, διαπιστώθηκε ότι το μεγαλύτερο πρόβλημα των παραγωγών και εκεί από όπου προέρχονται όλες τους οι ανάγκες είναι οι μεταβολές του καιρού. Διαμορφώθηκαν, λοιπόν, τέσσερις υπηρεσίες. «Η πρώτη θα ενοποιεί την κατάλληλη μέρα και το κατάλληλο χρονικό διάστημα για το άρρωμα του χωραφιού.

Η δεύτερη έχει να κάνει με την παρακολούθηση του χωραφιού καθ' όλη τη διάρκεια της καλλιεργητικής περιόδου, ώστε να γίνεται ακριβής λίπανση με βάση τις ανάγκες της εκμετάλλευσης. Η τρίτη υπηρεσία έχει να κάνει με την άρδευση. Μέσω των δορυφόρων, θα δίνονται ακριβείς οδηγίες για την ποσότητα του νερού, ανάλογα με τις διαφορετικές απαιτήσεις του χωραφιού, ενώ η τέταρτη θα δίνει

μία εκτίμηση της παραγωγής, έτσι ώστε να ξέρει ο γεωργός όσο το δυνατόν νωρίτερα και ακριβέστερα τι πρόκειται να πάρει σε απόδοση», τονίζει η Μ. Συμεωνίδου.

Όλα τα παραπάνω έχουν ως στόχο τη βελτιστοποίηση της παραγωγικής διαδικασίας, που θα οδηγήσει σε μείωση των περιβαλλοντικών επιπτώσεων, με τη χρήση λιγότερων φυτοφαρμάκων, λιπασμάτων, νερού και καυσίμων, αλλά και τις υψηλότερες αποδόσεις και, ως εκ τούτου, την αύξηση της κερδοφορίας και της ανταγωνιστικότητας.

Πιλοτική εφαρμογή

Οι αγρότες των δύο γεωργικών ενώσεων που θα συμμετάσχουν στην πιλοτική εφαρμογή, θα μπορούσαν, μαζί με τους ειδικούς, να κάνουν τις τελευταίες αλλαγές, αφού, πριν από την πρώτη εφαρμογή, οι εταιρείες θα επικοινωνούν μαζί, τις εκμεταλλεύσεις των αγροτών για να τους παρουσιάσουν την εφαρμογή. «Η εφαρμογή έχει ολοκληρωθεί. Το επόμενο χρονικό διάστημα θα πάμε στους γεωργούς για να κάνουμε τις τελευταίες αλλαγές και να πάμε σε πρώτη πιλοτική εφαρμογή από φέτος», αναφέρει η κα Συμεωνίδου, η οποία συνεχίζει λέγοντας πως η πιλοτική εφαρμογή θα γίνει στην Ελλάδα, τη Σερβία και την Ισπανία και οι αγρότες θα μπορούν να έχουν πρόσβαση στην εφαρμογή μέσω υπολογιστή, τμήμα ή ηλεκτρονικού ταχυδρομείου.

Τέλος, τονίζει πως αυτό που ευελιχιστούν από την πιλοτική εφαρμογή είναι να υπάρξει υψηλή αποδοτική από τους γεωργούς. «Να βρουν, δηλαδή, αυτή την εφαρμογή πραγματικά χρήσιμη και να τους βοηθήσει στην καθημερινότητά τους. Αυτό είναι το άρρωμα που έχουμε εμείς. Ο γεωργός να έχει ένα εργαλείο, το οποίο θα τον βοηθήσει».

Figure 13: APOLLO on the Greek agri - journal “ΥΠΑΙΘΡΟΣ”, published in June 2017.

1.9.3 Other countries

- ITALY: [Article and interview video](#) with the APOLLO coordinator Machi Simeonidou (DRAXIS) in the Italian Edizioni l'Informatore Agrario, 17 February 2017.
- International: [Article](#) in EARSC's EO mag, April 2017 Issue (see figure below).

Figure 14: APOLLO on EO mag (April 2017).

Impact/Progress: According to the key performance indicators defined in D7.1 “1st Dissemination, communication and marketing plan”, the overall target is to have 45 appearances in the media. So far APOLLO has appeared in 11 articles, radio/TV shows at national and international level, while 7 during the period M06-M12. These appearances had a major effect in engaging new people to get

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involved in APOLLO as shown from the other indicators above, especially in this second reporting period (M06-M12). APOLLO representatives will continue promoting APOLLO activities through media and as entering the more commercial phase, efforts are expected to be increased.

2 Conclusions

This Dissemination Report has provided an overview of the dissemination and marketing activities implemented in the scope of the APOLLO project, in accordance with the provisions of the Dissemination Plan “D7.1: Dissemination, communication and marketing plan” issued during the first months of the project (M03).

The effectiveness of these activities has been ensured by defining appropriate target groups, allowing the most relevant audiences to be reached with the most appropriate dissemination and communication tools and activities. The main aim is to keep the interested parties engaged with the project and its results, with the ultimate intention of converting them into customers.

APOLLO's presence on the media (TV, radio and press) through consortium representatives in the pilot countries but also abroad (i.e. APOLLO's coordinator presence in the Italian TV) has proved to be very successful. More than a dozen farmers and agricultural consultants in the pilots were interested to get involved in APOLLO and requested more information from local representatives. APOLLO also gained more than fifteen new Newsletter and trial user subscribers. In addition, representatives of relevant projects and individuals from various countries such as Sweden, Italia and Serbia, contacted the APOLLO team seeking ways of potential collaboration.

Participation in various events such as workshops, conferences and networking events is an important activity for expanding networks, creating partnerships, as well as promoting APOLLO. As a result of the various events at which APOLLO has been represented, a solid basis for future cooperation has been formed. Partners have successfully embarked on building networks of contacts who are interested in the APOLLO services regionally and in the EU. Involvement in the outreach activities mentioned above has allowed the enrichment of the market knowledge of the APOLLO team and has provided meaningful insights into the key competitors and their practices.

A wider audience has also been reached through the participation of APOLLO representatives in international conferences, as well as the publication of papers in specialised publications.

3 Annexes

Annex I: APOLLO Dissemination Report

APOLLO Dissemination Report

May-October 2016

This form is for reporting APOLLO dissemination activities during the above time period. Please note that events should be reported using the Event Report template available in Dropbox\APOLLO\Templates.

* Απαιτείται

Διεύθυνση ηλεκτρονικού ταχυδρομείου *

Η διεύθυνσή σας ηλεκτρονικού ταχυ...

Partner *

Επιλογή ▾

Activity type *

Επιλογή ▾

Date(s) and place of activity (if applicable)

Η απάντησή σας

Description of activity

Η απάντησή σας

Audience (size/demographics)

Η απάντησή σας

Key stakeholders

Η απάντησή σας

Feedback / impact

Η απάντησή σας

Promotional material used

Η απάντησή σας

Material produced (e.g. photos, videos, presentations etc.)

Η απάντησή σας

ΥΠΟΒΟΛΗ

Σελίδα 1 από 1

Μην υποβάλλετε ποτέ κωδικούς πρόσβασης μέσω των Φορμών Google.

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